

Protecting a Newly Planted Hedge in a Grazed Field

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Protection of a young plant with individual mesh and a wooden fence with high-tensile wires for cattle and sheep at Ferme des Pâtures

For livestock farmers, planting a hedge in a grazed plot is a profitable investment, but requires effective protection. Ferme des Pâtures, an organic dairy sheep and suckler cattle farm, has been practicing agroforestry since 2016. In total, more than 30 hectares have been planted with trees within the plots and windbreak hedges. Drawing on their experience, they strongly recommend installing electric fencing as soon as the plants are planted to protect the young trees from animals and wildlife. This protection is crucial during the first 2 to 3 years, when the risk of tree mortality is highest. During the first planting operation in 2016, lines of trees running north-south were planted every 26 meters over a 17-hectare area. The investment per tree was €35: €10 for the tree and its protection and €25 for the fencing. Fixed fencing, which is expensive to install and requires significant labor (two months of full-time work for one person), offers durability of 30 to 40 years. They are adapted to the needs of the herds, with low high-tensile wires for sheep and robust systems with wooden anchor posts for cattle. In addition to the fencing, individual sheaths and netting around the trunks reinforce the protection. The trees and their protection represented an initial investment of €18,000, 80% of which was funded by the water agency. Despite the investment they represent, these protection systems enable farmers to obtain a sustainable hedge, capable of improving biodiversity and soil protection, while contributing to grazing management. However, annual maintenance of these fences and trees is still necessary, but it is possible to invest in an under-fence shredder to improve efficiency, as is currently done at the Ferme des Pâtures and by other farmers.

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